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Marine derived polysaccharides loaded composite membranes

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Introduction: Ever increasing pollution control regulations and green material awareness paves way to find innovative material which can oversee the existing demands. Biocompatible materials from different resources may be a suitable alternative to conventional processes. Marine-derived components fall under this category and green seaweed polysaccharide can be utilized as an additive in material fabrication due to its enormous advantageous. Alginate, Carrageenan (three different forms) and Chitosan were well explored for various application in virgin and as a composite structure. Out of all these, green seaweed shows enormous growth and exhibit excellent potential in health, medicine, cosmetics and pollution control fields [1]. In this paper, we report the utilization of sulfated green seaweed polysaccharide in Polysulfone membrane fabrication process. For better membrane efficiency and water flux depends on membrane surface and cross-section morphology.

Methods: *Ulva Fasciata* samples were collected from coastal Gujarat, India. The sample was washed to remove epiphytes and shade dried. After complete drying, *Ulva* biomass powder was extracted [2] and dried. The obtained powder was further fine powdered by means of a ball mill (Retsch mixer mill MM 400, Germany) and stored at moisture-free conditions. The physical and chemical characterizations of the samples were performed to confirm purity and nature of the extracted compound. Elemental analysis (CHNS), protein, nitrogen, sulfate, ash content values were recorded. ATR-IR and XRD characterizations were performed to confirm ulvan property. PSf pellets (Udel P-3500, Solvay, USA), N, N dimethylformamide (DMF) (Merck, India) and Non-Woven polyester fabric (Filtration Sciences Corp., USA) were used in the current investigation. PSf membranes fabricated with Ulvan of suitable concentration was prepared and stored in deionized water for further investigations. The porosity, hydrophilicity, surface and cross-section morphology and surface roughness analysis of the membrane was monitored.

Results & Discussions: Ulvan was extracted from *Ulva fasciata* and analyzed for physicochemical properties, which matches with earlier reports. Different solvents (DMF, DMSO, THF, NMP) were also tried to prepare homogenous polymer dope solution and DMF seems to be perfect for the PSf/Ulvan composition. FTIR and TGA thermal analysis confirmed the presence of various functional group and homogenous distribution of ulvan on the fabricated membrane. The hydrophilic nature of the membrane was confirmed from the contact angle experimental image which proves the effect of ulvan on PSf membrane. Increase in ulvan concentration on the composite membrane completely alter surface roughness and hydrophilic nature. Similarly scanning electron microscope images reveal the morphological changes occurred on surface, cross-section. Presence of ulvan (sulfated polysaccharide) influence the phase-inversion kinetics according to concentration and alter morphologies. The current investigation supports growing interest and plethora of benefits of using seaweed derived polysaccharides as a promising alternative to fabricate multi-functional materials.

Conclusions: PSf membranes were prepared successfully with ulvan through phase-inversion process with controllable morphology and cross-section. Solvent effects on phase-inversion and homogenous membrane preparation extensively studied to understand the relationship between solvent and polymer components. Effect of ulvan concentration on membrane structures and can broaden the applications of PSf/Ulv composite membranes for pollution control applications.

Key words: Sustainable material, Sulfated polysaccharides, Polysulfone membrane

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